
Interoperable solutions for implementing holistic **FLEXi**bility
services in the distribution **GRID**

Dissemination and communication plan

Deliverable 9.1

WP9

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	RE → Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC)
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ABBREVIATIONS

PC: Project Coordinator

CA: Consortium Agreement

CC: Communication Committee

DoA: Description of Action

EC: European Commission

GA: General Assembly

IPR: Intellectual Property Right

KPI: Key Performance Indicator

M: Month

PH: Project Handbook

R&D: Research and Development

SC: Steering Committee

TP: Technical Partner

WP: Work Package

SME: Small and Medium Enterprise

DMP: Data Management Plan

H2020: Horizon 2020

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable represents the groundwork for **WP9 Communication and dissemination activities** as it is the outcome of the first task within this work package; *Task 9.1 Development of the Dissemination and Communication Strategy*. Furthermore, this deliverable is closely related to *Task 9.2 Dissemination and public communication actions* because they feed the structure and are the necessary input for all dissemination and communication activities.

This document is the initial plan for communication and dissemination of the FLEXIGRID project and includes the main activities that will be carried out for the entire duration of the project. The document sets the strategic framework for communication and dissemination of the project results and will be available to all project partners. The aim of the Communication and Dissemination Plan is to establish and run the visibility and communication infrastructure of the project so that all activities carried out during the project lifetime will be widely known in Europe.

Furthermore, this document is intended to be updated and adjusted as the project progresses. Finally, it holds a set of manuals to guide all consortium partners during their communication and dissemination actions.

The dissemination activities have been designed to target the key audiences and stakeholders and to maximize awareness of FLEXIGRID objectives and project activities.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan gives an overview of all dissemination opportunities identified through traditional communication channels such as event attendance (conferences, seminars, workshops, etc.), project publications (brochures, press releases, articles in professional journals, etc.) and project presentations (to various stakeholders and the general public).

CIRCE will coordinate and manage FLEXIGRID dissemination and communication activities. Nevertheless, all the project partners will be responsible to disseminate FLEXIGRID results through their communication channels and towards their existing communities.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Communication is a tool for supporting and strengthening the actions planned for the dissemination of impacts and results achieved in FLEXIGRID project. Therefore, this tool is being developed and defined right at the beginning of the project through a detailed and comprehensive communication strategy which will be developed with the participation of all partners. Furthermore, it should support internal communication and define rules and assign responsibilities among the partners of the consortium.

This communication plan provides an overview of the internal strategy among the project partners, the key messages about FLEXIGRID to be disseminated, the target audience and the channels through which they should be conveyed. It also explains the internal procedures for better organisation and reporting of the dissemination carried out as well as involving all the partners involved in order to achieve a greater impact.

The dissemination activities have been designed to target the key audiences and stakeholders and to maximize awareness of FLEXIGRID objectives and project activities. Any dissemination activities and publications in the project will acknowledge the Horizon 2020 Programme funding.

KPI tools and meters have been established to achieve a vision and improve the strategy for the future.

The communication strategy will comply with art. 29 of the Grant Agreement (GA) n° 864579 and will ensure the dissemination of the project results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium). The dissemination of results will ensure protection of the beneficiaries foreground and legitimate interests as stated in the GA.

2. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

2.1. Key Dissemination and Communication Objectives

To achieve the objectives of the FLEXIGRID project, an effective dissemination strategy must be developed and implemented. This strategy is deployed in the present communication and dissemination plan. The plan will be regularly updated to follow the progress of the project.

This communication and dissemination plan aims to establish clear and reliable standards, in order to ensure targeted and effective dissemination of the project objectives, activities and results. The strategy also foresees all methods, tools and channels of dissemination. It is expected that the implementation of this plan, together with the work of the partners, will achieve maximum awareness of the project activities and results. The main objectives to develop a communication and dissemination plan of the project are:

- Guarantee an effective communication of the project messages and activities at Local, National and EU level.
- Establish the project's messages.
- Identify methods, channels and instruments of communication and dissemination.
- Determine the topics to be disseminated: results, solutions and knowledge collected in the project.
- Define the responsibilities of partners in dissemination activities.
- Determine the tools for control and monitoring by the coordinator.
- Identify the dissemination KPIs, useful to measure the effectiveness and efficiency of the activities conducted.
- Illustrate how the project will cooperate with other EU-funded projects or related initiatives.

The communication and dissemination actions are performed throughout the whole duration of the project, progressing from initial awareness raising to the promotion of the FLEXIGRID deliverables. These actions will be supported by materials for communication which will be customized according to the targeted public (project partners, associations or entities, policy makers, governmental representatives, etc.).

The strategy will highlight the objectives, explained in detail in the project's proposal, and convey the key messages to as wide an audience as possible including all the above groups.

2.2. Purpose

The communication strategy has to support specific purposes such as:

- To convey to the general public the current state of the networks, specifically in the project's demonstrators.
- Explain the changes and benefits that the application of the solutions developed by FLEXIGRID will bring to reduce the barriers encountered, which are grouped into three levels: a) flexibility, b) reliability and c) economic efficiency.
- To disseminate the results obtained vis-à-vis potential final users and pave the way for exploitation of project final results.

- To disseminate the results obtained and the impact generated after the application of these solutions in the four demonstrators: Spain, Greece, Italy and Croatia.
- Replicate the dissemination made by partners through events, workshops or any other format that involves the transmission of knowledge of the work of FLEXIGRID.

2.3. Methodology

A strategic methodology has been designed to establish a procedure to be followed by all the partners to publish effective communications of the project. The following table show the FLEXIGRID Communication procedure:

Figure 1. FLEXIGRID Communication Methodology

2.4. Key messages

The following table defines some of the actions that will be carried out during the execution of the project that can be disseminated to achieve a greater knowledge of the work carried out by the partners of FLEXIGRID, as well as the objectives to be achieved through the project. Together with the described actions, the target group of interest to which they are addressed is established, as well as the most appropriate communication channels for this purpose.

KEY MESSAGE	TARGET GROUP OF INTEREST	CHANNELS
Announcing the regional workshops and sectorial analysis	General Public	Internal channels, mailing to platforms and associations Press release to general media Press release to specialized media (TV, radio, press) Partners' Social networks –partners' Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn profiles Project's Website Flyer and Posters if needed
Announcing specific activities (demos, new value chains, etc.)	General Public, Projects partners	Internal channels, mailing to platforms and associations Press release to general media Press release to specialized media (TV, radio, press) Partners' Social networks –partners' Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn profiles, partners' websites Project's Website
Announcing flexigrid's presence at national or international fairs or events	General Public, Scientific public	Internal channels, mailing to platforms and associations Partners' Social networks –partners' Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn profiles, partners' websites
Announcing article published in scientific magazine	Scientific public, Projects partners	Internal channels, mailing to platforms and associations Partners' Social networks –partners' Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn profiles, partners' websites
Announcing new dissemination material explaining the project such as a video, infographics...	General Public, Projects partners	Internal channels, mailing to platforms and associations Press release to general media Press release to specialized media (TV, radio, press) Partners' Social networks –partners' Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn profiles Project's Website
Announcing a new public deliverable	General Public, Projects partners, Scientific public	Internal channels Partners' Social networks –partners' Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn profiles Project's Website
Announcing new results obtained	General Public, Projects partners, Scientific public	Internal channels, mailing to platforms and associations Press release to general media Press release to specialized media (TV, radio, press) Partners' Social networks –partners' Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn profiles Project's Website

Table 1. FLEXIGRID Key Messages

2.5. Disseminations Channels and Communication Tools

An essential part of this strategy involves the design of communication tools to maximize the project's impacts. These are based on the internal communication tools that are already used by the partners, and the external communication channels that are the tools that will be created in the framework of the project.

The following tools are the different ways that FLEXIGIRD will exploit to carry out the diffusion. All of this have been categorising in two main groups; External communication channels and FLEXIGRID communication tools.

PARTNERS	WEBSITE	NEWSLETTER	TV/RADIO	SOCIAL MEDIA
ATOS	www.atos.net	no	no	Twitter LinkedIn Youtube Facebook
CAP	www.capenergies.fr	no	Contacts with local and regional media	Twitter LinkedIn
CIRCE	www.fcirce.es	no	Contacts with local, regional and national media	Twitter Facebook LinkedIn Youtube
EDYNA	www.edyna.net	no	no	no
HEP-ODS	www.hep.hr/ods/	no	Contacts with local and regional media if needed	Youtube
IOSA	makryammos-hotel	no	Contacts with local and regional media	Facebook Instagram
LINKS	www.linksfoundation.com	no	Contacts with local and regional media	Twitter Youtube LinkedIn Facebook
ORMAZABAL	www.ormazabal.com	no	no	LinkedIn Twitter Youtube

SELTA	www.selta.com	no	Contacts with local and national sector / generalist editors/journalists	LinkedIn Twitter Youtube
UNICAN	www.web.unican.es	no	Contacts with local and regional media Press department with media creation capacity	Twitter Facebook LinkedIn Youtube Instagram
UNIZG-FER	www.fer.unizg.hr/en	yes	Contacts with national media	LinkedIn
VIESGO	www.viesgodistribucion.com	no	Contacts with local and regional media	Twitter Facebook LinkedIn Youtube Instagram
ZIV	www.zivautomation.com	no	sector media	LinkedIn Youtube

Table 2. Existing communication channels

TOOL	COMMENTS
WEBSITE	The domain of the website is www-flexigrid-h2020.eu Website of the FLEXIGRID project where the objectives, expected impacts, use cases and demonstrators where the solutions will be implemented are explained. Besides, the website will be a space where all the articles, dissemination materials and news will be published to help spread the achievements of FLEXIGRID

<p>HASHTAG</p>	<p>Nowadays social networks are saturated with accounts. For a new account to have some impact you need to make daily publications as well as interact with other users.</p> <p>From previous experiences, we know that in the life of a project it is not possible to reach a decent number of people through a new account. For this reason, we have thought of creating a hashtag for the project and, taking advantage of the influence of the project partners' networks, making the publications through them, including the hashtag in all of publications. With this we achieve that in any social network (linkedin, facebook and twitter), looking for the established hashtag will appear all the publications made so far and the interactions that it has had.</p> <p>The hashtag of the FLEXIGRID project will be #FLEXIGRIDproject</p>
<p>PRESS RELEASE TEMPLATES</p>	<p>Templates will be made available to members with form news or press release to be completed in English. This template will be sent to the coordinator for publication on the project website. If it is considered of interest, it will be sent to all partners so that it can be translated into their native languages and sent to local media for further dissemination.</p>
<p>SURVEY COMMUNICATION FOLLOW-UP</p>	<p>An excel template will be made available to the partners in which each partner must record all the dissemination actions carried out. This template will serve as a record and follow-up of the dissemination of the project and will be permanently in the files of the Microsoft TEAMS tool.</p>

Table 3. FLEXIGRID communication tools

2.6. Acknowledgment of EU funding

All communication and dissemination materials will include the following specific sentence and the EU emblem (flag):

Figure 2. FLEXIGRID EU Acknowledgment

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

Besides, any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

It is foreseen that all the equipment purchased for the project will include a sticker with the following specific sentence:

Figure 3. FLEXIGRID EU Acknowledgment for product or equipment

2.7. Dissemination and communication materials

Website

The project website is one of the main communication tools for any EU funded project. It provides easy and quick access to the project results for a wide audience.

The main project website is available at www.flexigrid-h2020.eu and will be updated on a regular basis with the latest results and news concerning the project.

The FLEXIGRID website includes the following content:

- ✓ *Project Homepage* – general overview of the whole website
- ✓ *The project* – general information, objectives and solutions of the project
- ✓ *Partners* – list of project partners including their logos, website address, a brief description and main task and responsibilities within the project
- ✓ *Demos* – Including the eight uses cases and the information of the four demosites
- ✓ *Publications* – a repository of reports/deliverables that is available to the general public
- ✓ *News*

Interoperable solutions for implementing holistic FLEXibility services in the distribution GRID

Figure 4. FLEXIGRID website homepage

Brochures

To promote the FLEXIGRID project to a wider audience, a trifold in English (and potentially in partners-based local languages for distribution at local events) will be produced. The brochure will include a description of the project, its background, and goals as well as a list of the partners involved. The brochure is presented by the FLEXIGRID partners, during conferences, workshops as well as shows and is also distributed to internal staff, visitors, partners, and clients.

Roll-up

A roll-up of the project will be elaborated that can be printed by any partner of the project with the objective of decorating scenarios of events or stands of fairs as well as in meetings where stakeholders are present

Press Releases

FLEXIGRID press releases aim to record all the activities of the project and inform the general public about the project. They are available following this link: <http://flexigrid-h2020.eu/news/>

Flexigrid: Interoperable solutions for implementing flexibility services in the distribution grid

In order to reach the Paris Agreement objectives and achieve a more sustainable energy system, the EU is aiming at increasing up to at least 32% the share of renewables in energy consumption. At this purpose FLEXIGRID project will develop a set of solutions to address, under a cost-efficient basis, [...]

Figure 5. Press Release published on FLEXIGRID website

Social Media

Information on the FLEXIGRID project developments and its results will be published on the websites of the different partners as well as promoted via their Social Media accounts.

At any moment of FLEXIGRID lifetime partners are more than welcome and invited to share and promote FLEXIGRID via press and social media using whether their personal or professional account. All the posts in social media are encouraged to include the unique hashtag #FLEXIGRIDproject.

General Project Presentation

A generic PowerPoint presentation was drafted at the beginning of the project. Based on the project outcome, this presentation will be updated regularly. The presentation contains a non-confidential overview of the project which is used by the members for dissemination purposes. This presentation can be found here <http://www.flexigrid-h2020.eu/overview-of-the-project-flexigrid/>

Public Deliverables and Reports

All the public deliverables and reports will be available on the FLEXIGRID website under documents section <http://www.flexigrid-h2020.eu/deliverables/>

Poster

A poster with the general information of the project: objectives, use cases, demonstrators and project partners was produced and presented at the BRIDGE event.

All graphic materials will be updated throughout the project including news and results. These materials will be found in the publications section of the website <http://www.flexigrid-h2020.eu/dissemination-material/>

Video

A final video will be produced highlighting the main outcomes of the FLEXIGRID project. The video will be produced with a mix of footage, animations and infographics to address stakeholders at large and the general public. It will be hosted on the website and distributed online to all partners' platforms and information multipliers.

Articles and media publications

Throughout the project, several articles will be published in the media, conferences and magazines of the relevant sector showing the results and progress achieved.

2.8. Dissemination and communication events

Workshops

Four workshops are planned throughout the project, one in each of the cities with a demonstrator.

The aim is to disseminate the project results, mobilize stakeholders and establish deep ties with relevant platforms, networks, associations and other related projects. Moreover, key partners will present the project in at least 2 main national and European events related to Island issues.

Final Event

At the conclusion of the project, the consortium will organize a conference where results will be explained. Moreover, in this final conference, the replication strategy beyond FLEXIGRID project and the real expectations concerning the new developed technologies and value chains will also be explained.

The final conference (including a webinar) will be organized in Brussel. Synergies with other EU funded projects and initiatives will be exploited to increase the outreach of potential stakeholders, organize joint events, exchange knowledge, experience and best practices, and stimulate discussions among key players, the scientific and industrial community.

3. STAKEHOLDER'S ROLE

3.1. Contribution from internal and external stakeholders

Internal stakeholders on the FLEXIGRID project are project partners, whereas policymakers, industry associations, EU authorities and the wide public in general, are regarded as external stakeholders. It is expected that both internal and external stakeholders will contribute to FLEXIGRID communications and dissemination activities.

The stakeholders will have all the elements described above to support the dissemination of the project.

3.2. Tracking & Reporting of dissemination activities

All partners will play a role in the dissemination of the results and their interest and opportunities will be identified through the "Dissemination Activities Excel". This is a dedicated survey template to be filled (and updated) by the partners during the project. In addition, the partner responsible for each deliverable will be asked to establish the dissemination potential of the deliverable prior to its submission. The deliverables of the project will be used as milestones to monitor the progress of dissemination activities.

According to the GA each partner should disseminate its results, taking into account the confidentiality agreements set in the GA and CA:

Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must — as soon as possible — 'disseminate' its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium).

Any partner that intends to disseminate (participate, launch or host any related activity) foreground of FLEXIGRID shall notice the project coordinator and dissemination manager as soon as possible and at least 45 days in advance, including the information that will be disseminated and the forum.

3.3. Cooperation obligations and rules for published or unpublished results or background

A partner shall not include in any dissemination activity another partner's results or background without obtaining the owning party's prior written approval, unless they are already published.

The partners undertake to cooperate to allow the timely submission, examination, publication and defence of any dissertation or thesis for a degree which includes their results or background subject to the confidentiality and publication provisions agreed in the Consortium Agreement.

The name of the parties or any of their logos or trademarks cannot be used in advertising or publicity without partners' prior written approval.

3.4. Schedule for project partners' responsibilities in press notes

Although CIRCE coordinates and manages FLEXIGRID dissemination and communication activities, all the partners are responsible to disseminate the results through their communication channels and towards their existing communities. In addition, the partner

responsible for each deliverable will be asked to establish the dissemination potential of the deliverable prior to its submission.

For a better replication and impact of the action, the partner generating a dissemination activity will fill in the dedicated press release template in English and send it to CIRCE for publication on the project page. If it is considered of interest, CIRCE will send the press release to the other partners to be disseminated through their channels.

3.5. Synergies and interaction with other projects and initiatives

FLEXIGRID will forge communication with other EU projects related to smart grids, in particular with those participating in BRIDGE. This will promote synergies with other projects and the establishment of cluster participation in events and publications, promoting the dissemination potential of FLEXIGRID website by sharing news and links. These synergies will facilitate project partners to disseminate results to other H2020 projects.

PROJECT NAME & LOGO	BRIEF DESCRIPTION, PARTNERS INVOLVED AND MAIN LINKS WITH FLEXIGRID
	<p>Energy services demonstrations of demand response, flexibility and energy efficiency based on metering data – <i>Partners: CIRCE</i></p> <p>The project puts in place five large-scale demonstrators for the deployment of novel services in the retail market due to a virtual ICT environment to exchange data and services and advanced monitoring and control systems. Key results and conclusions on architectures, market opportunities and data accessibility will be transferred to FLEXIGRID for the development of WP8 and WP9.</p>
	<p>Smart TSO-DSO interaction schemes, market architectures and ICT Solutions for integration of ancillary services from demand side management and distributed generation</p> <p><i>Partners: EDYNA</i></p> <p>The SmartNet project arises from the need to find answers and propose new practical solutions to the increasing integration of Renewable Energy Sources in the existing electricity transmission network.</p>
	<p>New cost-effective business models for flexible Smart Grids</p> <p><i>Partners: HYPER</i></p> <p>NOBEL GRID provides advanced tools and ICT services to all actors in the Smart Grid and retail electricity market to ensure benefits from cheaper prices, more secure and stable grids and clean electricity.</p>

Massive integration of power electronic devices – *Partners: CIRCE*
MIGRATE will develop and validate technology-based solutions making possible the management of the growing penetration of power electronics-connected generation and consumption. As a result, an easier integration of distributed generation will be achieved, which is crucial for FLEXIGRID.

Wide scale demonstration of Integrated Solutions & business models for European smartGRID

Partners: HYPER

WiseGRID will provide a set of solutions and technologies to increase the smartness, stability and security of an open, consumer-centric European energy grid. The project provides services for the actors of the distribution network in different scenarios to promote more sustainable energy grids, empowering the prosumers and enabling the establishment of a near real-time pan European energy balancing market.

Integrated Smart GRID Cross-Functional Solutions for Optimized Synergetic Energy Distribution, Utilization & Storage Technologies

Coordinator: ATOS

inteGRIDy pursues facilitating the optimal and dynamic operation of the Distribution Grid, fostering the stability of the electricity grid and coordination of distributed energy resources, Virtual Power Plants and innovative collaborative storage schemes within a continuously increased share of renewable energy.

Indian and European Local Energy Communities for Renewable Integration and the Energy Transition – *Partners: CIRCE*

A concept composed by mobile storage systems combined with forecasting, DR programmes and islanding capabilities of local energy communities will be implemented in 4 EU and 1 Indian networks. Main results from IELECTRIX will be used to optimize flexibility and stability of the MT-HV grid.

Maximizing the impact of innovative energy approaches in the EU islands

Coordinator: CIRCE

To foster the deployment of innovative solutions for the EU islands decarbonization by developing and demonstrating at three Lighthouse Islands a set of interventions linked to seven replicable use cases, whose results will validate an Investment Planning Tool that will be then demonstrated at four Follower Islands for the development of four associated Action Plans.

Real proven solutions to enable active demand and distributed generation flexible integration, through a fully controllable LOW Voltage and medium voltage distribution grid – Partners: ZIV

This project focuses on addressing the constraints and needs arisen from poor observability of LV grid, local accumulation of distributed generation, risks and difficulties. in managing the distribution network, aging infrastructure and social and environmental restrictions that inhibit grid development.

A novel smart grid architecture that facilitates high RES penetration through innovative markets towards efficient interaction between advanced electricity grid management and intelligent stakeholders.

Partners: UNIZG-FER

The goal of FLEXGRID is to facilitate energy sector stakeholders (DSOs, TSOs, ESPs and RESPs) to: i) easily and effectively create advanced Energy Services (ESs), ii) interact in a dynamic and efficient way with their environment (electricity grid) and the remaining of the stakeholders, and iii) automate and optimize the planning and the operation of their ESs.

Table 4. Project synergies

4. INTERNAL PROCEDURES & KPIS

4.1. Procedure internal communication

The following table shows the different procedures to be followed according the different types of publications that its plan to be developed during the whole project. If a new type of publications can be detected this diagram will be updated on the next versions of this deliverable.

Figure 6. FLEXIGRID internal communication procedure

4.2. Tools

The tools established by the project are currently:

- The Excel Communication Tool;
- Microsoft TEAMS will be used as a communication channel between partners, document repository and as a tool to perform task sharing through Planner. In addition, public documents will be uploaded to the FLEXIGRID website.

- The templates provided by CIRCE to the partners and specified in *the DV 9.5 Visual Identity and Set*;
- The hashtag #FLEXIGRIDPROJECT for all communications in social networks.

This section will be updated in the next deliverables according to the tools or needs that could be demanded during the project implementation.

4.3. Measurable results

Communication activities shall be monitored according to a set of quantitative and qualitative success indicators. The evaluation of communication activities will determine the degree to which the communication objectives have been reached, and the relationship between the outcomes and the efforts made to reach the goals. This analysis will help the project to better understand facilitators and barriers of a successful communication and will serve to refine the communication activities accordingly. The following tools will be used to obtain these KPIs:

Google Analytics

Regarding the project website, Google analytics will be implemented in February 2020 and it will give an overview of sessions and users. It will be used to continually measure the performance and activity of visitors so that impact can be easily assessed.

Number of publications

Different publications will be released during the FLEXIGRID project: press releases, articles, scientific articles, etc. Published articles will be monitored as well as press releases sent to the media. For each press release sent to the local media, the partner must collect the impact clipping.

Media coverage

Partners are encouraged to contact the media (either general or specialized) in order to increase the project's visibility and to spread the activities and results foreseen in it.

This can be achieved by:

- The emission of a press release
- Inviting media to the main events celebrated during the project.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The Communication and Dissemination Plan aims at ensuring an adequate knowledge transfer to the project partners and all other interested parties in FLEXIGRID.

Several tools have been or will be developed to put in place this strategy: website, brochure, video, articles, leaflet, workshops, events, press releases, among others.

Interaction with other projects and initiatives that enhance the project results and help to achieve the objectives is particularly relevant in FLEXIGRID.

As described in this deliverable, the dissemination and communication plan is an important and dynamic element of the project which needs to be updated periodically and deployed along the project life cycle.

Furthermore, this document is intended to be updated in M18 also M36, and adjusted as the project progresses. Finally, it holds a set of manuals to guide all consortium partners during their communication and dissemination actions.